

AUTISM MYTHS THAT MENTAL HEALTHCARE PRACTITIONERS SHOULD KNOW WHEN WORKING WITH CLIENTS WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER

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Not much was known or noticed about autism spectrum disorder (ASD) before 1980s. However, as the prevalence of the condition started climbing higher and became widespread throughout the world, the alarm bell sounded loud and clear. The latest US data published in 2014 announced “the prevalence at 1 in 68 (up from 1 in 150 in 2002)” (Jarrett, 2015, p.289). In Singapore, it has been reported that there are about 24,000 people with ASD and the Ministry of Health’s Child Development Program diagnosed 610 preschoolers with the condition in 2012, up from 360 in 2005 (Tai, 2013, p.B1). The panic button was pressed and both professionals and parents with children identified with ASD became more aware of the so-called autism epidemic worldwide (Taylor, 2007). Parents are beginning to question what has gone wrong ... why their children have autism. They sought all kinds of help including both conventional intervention and complementary and alternative treatments. Suddenly, the profile of ASD was elevated enormously with high-profile personalities such as Daniel Tammet (a mathematics genius) and Dr Temple Grandin (an animal welfare advocate) reported in both mass and social media.

Identifying and Defining Autism

Autism was first described by Dr Leo Kanner in 1943. Dr Hans Asperger, in 1944, described about a mild form of autism associated with high functioning and normal or near-normal language development (also known as Asperger’s syndrome). In 2013, the American Psychiatric Association removed Asperger’s syndrome from the new diagnostic criteria for ASD to accommodate people with autism of varying degrees of severity. Chia (2012a) provides a more inclusive definition of ASD: “a neuro-developmental syndrome of constitutional origin (genetic) and whose cause could also be epigenetic, and its onset is usually around first three years of birth, with empathizing or mentalizing deficits that result in a triad of impairments in communication, social interaction, and imagination, with manifestation of repetitive stereotyped behaviors, but may, on the other hand, display (especially by autistic savants) or hide (especially by autistic crypto-savants) a strong systemizing drive that accounts for a distinct triad of strengths in good attention to detail, deep narrow interests, and islets of ability” (p.239).

Mental healthcare practitioners working with parents who have children with ASD as well as youth and adults with ASD need to understand the causes and the treatments for ASD. Currently, nobody is able to pinpoint the exact causes of ASD nor

anyone is able to say there is one-size-fit-all treatment for individuals with ASD.

Common Misconceptions about Autism

The general public is often ill informed about ASD. One common misconception about ASD is that “children with ASD are diseased, and so parents should get medical and/or educational advice and help for them” (Chia, 2012c, p.24).

Many think that individuals with autism lack alertness, real emotions or empathy, are unable to understand the mental lives of others, are intellectually challenged, and the list goes on. Jarrett (2015) distinguishes between two aspects of empathy. The first one is the cognitive component, i.e., “the mental skill of standing in another person’s shoes” (Jarrett, 2015, p.291). The second one is the emotional component, i.e., “about whether you are moved by another person’s pain or happiness” (Jarrett, 2015, p.291). According to Jarrett (2015), children with ASD struggle with the cognitive component but are normal on the emotional component. The misconception that people with ASD lack empathy is based on the faulty mirror neuron system theory, which proposes that ASD is the result of a malfunction of the mirror neuron system. In a recent study by Hamilton (2013), no evidence has been found to support the theory of faulty mirror neuron system, with one exception that ASD is associated with less susceptibility to emotional contagion.

It is possible that the general public has yet to develop a sense of revulsion to such portraits of fellow humans. Chia (2012c) argues that “[T]he current biases are probably based on two misconceptions. The first is that autism is often described as a triad of impairments in communication, social interaction and flexibility of imagination or behavior, impairments often viewed as life failures. This is an inaccurate portrayal” (p.24). A wider definition of ASD basing on different routes of information processing, atypical cognitive and biologically defined markers is needed so that individuals with ASD can be recognized as people with a diversity of outcomes, including successes and failures. “The second misconception is that those with autism face major life challenges and are problematic. This is not totally true” (Chia, 2012c, p.24). While many of these individuals with ASD are observed to be giving problems and have experienced fewer successes in life as reported in a typical research study, it is most likely the case in a true population sample of people with ASD. In fact, it is due to selection bias that current ASD research has begun to recognize.

We want to reiterate that it is time to recognize the misleading stereotypes that create misconceptions about people with ASD, be they children or adults.

Having worked with many teachers and parents of children with ASD over past decades, we have gathered the following two main strands of autism myths that we want to share with fellow practitioners should they come across such cases in their professional work.

Strand 1: Myths underlying the Causes of Autism

The causes of ASD are often idiopathic, i.e., of unknown origin or *not otherwise specified* – a phrase that has been used in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM) published by the American Psychiatric Association.

One of the myths about the cause of ASD is that it was caused by the triple MMR (measles, mumps, rubella) vaccine, basing on the now debunked study published in *The Lancet* in 1998 (but has since been retracted by the journal in 2010) of the British pediatrician Dr Andrew Wakefield and his co-authors (see Deer, 2004). As a result of Wakefield's fraudulent study, many campaigns against MMR vaccination have been organized and held worldwide resulting in subsequent measles outbreaks – or measles epidemic – throughout the world. The Singapore Health Ministry has also assured the public that MMR vaccines are safe and found no link between the vaccines and autism (Bey, 2012).

Another damaging myth is the claim that thiomersal – a mercury-based preservative – found vaccines resulted in autism. According to Jarrett (2015), the current scientific community, backed by the Institute of Medicine, the World Health Organization, and others, has argued that there is no causal link between thiomersal-containing vaccines and autism.

A third claim is about the link between obesity and autism reported in *Today* (2012, April 10). Researchers today have made great strides in understanding the phenotype of obesity, with major efforts being directed towards assessing the interactions of genes and environment in the obesity epidemic. Family studies have also indicated indirectly that obesity has a genetic component. However, unlike obesity, no environmental factor per se has yet been identified or established with certainty to account for ASD. "Environment can mean everything in the world, from chemicals to diet and lifestyle, which have been identified as the culprits of obesity. ASD studies examining various environmental factors are still inconclusive" (Chia, 2012b, p.24).

With regards to the genotype of ASD and its link to obesity, the genetics of ASD is far too complex. Although researchers have managed to identify certain variants of a single chemical base along the DNA strand, called single nucleotide polymorphisms of the FTO gene located on chromosome 16p that appear to correlate with ASD and obesity, the linkage analysis has been inconclusive. Moreover, a sequence of more than 700 genes has been located from individuals with ASD and it accounts for more than a small fraction of the condition (Tai, 2013). According to Chia (2013a), studies have also found that strongly associated with ASD are two genetic disorders: tuberous sclerosis complex (TSC) and fragile-X syndrome (FXS). In fact, 17 per cent to 61 per cent of those with TSC also have ASD, while 0.4 per cent to 9 per cent of those with ASD have TS. Similarly, about 3 per cent to 5 per cent of those with FXS have ASD, and 2.5 per cent to 4 per cent of those with ASD have FXS. There is still a lot more to be done in the field of ASD research.

There are also two other claims (see Lim, 2011): the first claim is about parental age and ASD are positively associated; and the other claim is the maternal exposure to environmental tobacco smoke can result in high risk of ASD. To the first claim, Chia (2011) cautions that although parental age and ASD are positively linked, correlation does not equal causation. In scientific research, Chia (2011) argues, correlations studies are never used exclusively to claim a cause. "The genetics of autism is complex. Linkage analysis has been inconclusive. Reports on autism and parental age have also yielded conflicting results on whether mothers, fathers, or both, contribute to increased risk" (Chia, 2011, p.38). To the second claim, Chia (2011) argues that the misconception that environmental factor equals environmental toxin, and Lim (2011) points to environmental tobacco smoke in his argument. To date, Chia (2011) argues, "no environmental factor per se has yet been identified to account for ASD, let alone changes in autism prevalence" (p.38).

A recent scare report has claimed about an unexpected link between ASD and cancer genes (Kolata, 2013). Chia (2013b) argues that the findings of the reported study apply to only a small proportion (10 per cent) of people with ASD, especially those with mutation in the Pten gene that can cause cancer. Moreover, the study did not mention other ASD-associated disorders such as TSC and FXS. Individuals with TSC often have tumors that may cause serious problems on vital organs such as the heart, kidneys, eyes, lungs and skin. Although the overall cancer risk associated with TSC is low, those with the condition do face an increased risk of a specific type of brain cancer known as giant cell astrocytoma and kidney cancer. The Pten and TSC genes are not the same although they are part of the same network. The cytogenetic location of the Pten gene is in the deletion of the chromosome 10q23, which has long been associated with behavioral and neuro-developmental abnormalities, including intellectual disability, autism, hyperactivity and other psychiatric disorders. In other words, tuberous sclerosal individuals with ASD face a higher risk of cancer than autistic individuals with TSC.

It is our responsibility as mental healthcare professionals not to be too quick to accept new findings of studies on ASD, but be discerning to provide accurate information about it so that appropriate follow-up action can be taken next.

Strand 2: Myths underlying the Autism Treatments

There are many dangerous claims about fictitious "miracle" cures for ASD and hence, the myths that underlie the autism treatments. Many of these unproven, unscientific claims include special diets, megavitamin therapy, secretin injection, cranio-sacral therapy, chelation therapy to animal-assisted therapy. Findings from a survey study done by Chia and Kee (2013) to determine why many parents with children with disabilities sought complementary and alternative medicine/treatments (CAM/T) suggest that they "make them their choices based on the qualities of the provider, desire for individualized treatments, and their perception of overall effectiveness rather than efficacy. Other reasons ... include a positive valuation of CAM/T, the ineffectiveness of conventional or orthodox treatment for their complaint and dissatisfaction with care and communication with professionals providing the treatment" (p.38).

For instance, while chelation therapy has been used successfully to treat people with heavy metal poisoning, it has also been promoted as a cure for ASD by Yeo (2006) in a letter written to

Today claiming that according to the US-based Autism Research Institute (ARI), there is “considerable success in treating autism with a protocol that includes dietary management, vitamin/mineral supplementation and heavy metal detoxification” (p.18). Chia (2006) rebutted Yeo by citing that “Dr Bernard Rimland, ARI director, has made it known through mass media and the ARI website that chelation is not used to treat autism, but to treat heavy metal overload, which is a major cause of autism and retardation” (p.18). Moreover, the US Foods and Drugs Administration has never approved the use of any chelation in treating ASD. Even if it did work on one child with ASD or somehow the child responded positively to the treatment, it does not mean that chelation will work for all children with autism. This is because autism is not a disorder per se but a syndrome with many autistic-like subtypes.

Finally, it is the mental healthcare practitioners’ responsibility not to give false or high hopes that ASD can be cured but to advise parents and/or clients of the benefits, side-effects and dangers of such “miracle” treatments.

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Helping our clients create a readiness for change, and rise above their present issues/concerns!

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life s/he made a decision to act and respond in certain ways, albeit possibly unconsciously.

According to my main hypnosis mentor, the masterful Gil Boyne, there are three primary factors that create a readiness for change (the following three factors are taken directly from his teachings):

The first is based on the price one places on suffering, be it mental, physical, or emotional.

The second factor is psychic/emotional boredom and/or overwhelming anxiety—life-affirming activity or life-negating activity.

The third factor is the actual realization that "change is possible". Readiness for change depends on the creative value of suffering-mental, physical, or emotional/psychic. (When we have suffered enough we can overcome our fear of change). Overwhelming anxiety triggering either life-affirming (reaching out for help) or life-negating (entering into addictions) activity. The realization that change is possible by mobilizing and using one’s own inner power. (Our altered perception enables us to overcome a conditioned disbelief in our ability to use our inner power creatively.)

The foundation of a belief can change from the inside out, having the client choose a new belief and acting accordingly. Or, it can change from the outside in, behaving differently to create new information, and then change the foundation. According to a Harvard School of Health Science Study, people decide how they feel about someone in two seconds. It's unconscious. It's the fight-or-flight response. They just pick up on signals that someone gives them. Basically, they are feeling that they are either safe or not with somebody. If they feel safe, and like us, they look for opportunities to say 'yes' and agree, and tend to see the best in us. The keys: Trust, clarity and emotional impact, have to happen simultaneously. Hopefully, this is how our clients view us.

The person mentioned above might never change her opinion. And, if she continues getting good, lasting results with her clients, I am certainly not one to argue with that.

“Thank you so much for your quick reply. I am very impressed with IMDHA and how quickly you all respond and how friendly you all are!”

Shawn Mercer, British Columbia, CANADA

I wish to take the opportunity to thank the association; I really appreciate the material that is available and have picked up so much valuable information.”

Julie Roelofse, Cape Town, SOUTH AFRICA